

METHODS OF DEVELOPING SPORTS SKILLS IN THE TRAINING OF CHESS PLAYERS IN UZBEKISTAN

Rashidov Azizbek Ulugbekovich

Uzbek state university of physical culture and sports

Doctor of philosophy in pedagogy(PhD), associated professorEmail:

furion80@mail.ru

ORCID 0009-0001-6118-1197

Annotation The article examines the specifics of training highly qualified chess players, taking into account the psychological and pedagogical conditions and the specifics of the sports training system in Uzbekistan. Key components of strategic mastery are defined, such as combination vision, positional sense and calculation of options. The stages of long-term sports training are analyzed, the importance of basic and additional techniques in the formation of an individual playing style is emphasized.

Keywords: chess mastery, strategic thinking, training of chess players, educational and training process, psychological and pedagogical conditions, long-term sports training, Uzbekistan, state program, children's and youth chess schools, popularization of chess.

INTRODUCTION Training of top-level athletes is one of the priority tasks of modern sports science. This goal is achieved through the optimal organization of the educational and training process. The key principle of its effective construction should be the systematic preparation of athletes for successful performances in competitions. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account all the factors influencing this process. In this regard, there is a need to accurately determine the indicators. These indicators characterize the level of sports training of a chess player[1].

Chess is one of the oldest sports. It has survived to this day. The last major change in the rules of the game was made in the 16th century. Over such a long period, a significant number of chess publications have appeared. They examine various aspects of the theory and practice of chess. In specialized literature, much less attention is paid to the means and methods of training chess players. This concerns various stages of long-term sports training[2].

Despite this, at different times, famous coaches and chess players have dealt with the problems of training high-level athletes. Among them, we can highlight M.A. Vershinin (2002, 2005), I.V. Mikhailova (2005), M.R. Kobalia (2007) and

others. Their works reveal the essence of training a chess player. They also consider the factors that influence his athletic achievements. In addition, these works offer methods for organizing the educational and training process.

METHODS The systems of preparation for competitions proposed by different authors are similar in many ways. However, there are significant differences in approaches to determining the indicators. These indicators reflect the level of various aspects of an athlete's preparedness.

The object of the study is the sports training of chess players. Their competitive activity in children's and youth sports organizations is also an object.

Subject of the research are the means, methods and forms of training activities of chess players. These means and methods are aimed at developing the skills of solving strategic problems in a chess game. This is relevant at the stage of sports improvement.

Purpose of the study is to develop a method for developing strategic mastery in chess players. The goal is also to scientifically substantiate this method. This is necessary at the stage of their sports improvement.

RESULTS The mastery of a chess player depends on the quality of his strategy and consists of three key qualities - combination vision, positional sense and calculation of variations. They are based on experience and require creative thinking. Each of these qualities can be defined as follows.

a) Combination vision is the ability of a chess player to find bright ideas. These ideas are often connected with the sacrifice of chess material. Usually, this is a change in the usual correlations of the value of the pieces.

b) Positional intuition is the ability of a chess player to identify the main content of a position. It helps to choose the optimal arrangement of pieces taking into account the opponent's actions. This creates the prerequisites for assessing the position and building a plan.

c) Variation calculation is the ability of a chess player to mentally analyze a sequence of positions. These positions arise when considering the consequences of various candidate moves[3].

The resulting qualities are of significant importance in assessing the level of sportsmanship of a chess player. This is the ability to evaluate a position and the ability to combine, that is, to carry out combinations. These qualities can be described as follows.

a) Positional evaluation is the ability of a chess player to generalize information obtained from a deep analysis of a position. This quality includes positional intuition and calculation of short, unforced variations.

b) Combination is the ability to carry out combinations. It includes combination vision and effective calculation of long forced variations.

A chess player's knowledge places demands on his memory. This includes both specific information (for example, precise opening and endgame knowledge) and information about typical playing techniques at all stages of the game, especially in the middlegame. These parameters form the basis of strategic mastery.

The structure of strategic mastery is an interconnected complex of three components. They mediate the mental and practical actions in the educational, training and competitive activities of chess players. These are the cognitive, operational-functional and analytical components.

The cognitive component reflects the results of the active educational and training work of the chess player. It is characterized by the volume, breadth, depth and systematicity of knowledge. In combination with practical skills, this knowledge allows the chess player to use various techniques and methods to solve problems during training and competitions. The leading component of the cognitive component is accumulated knowledge. They are necessary for setting and solving professional problems in accordance with the needs and interests of the individual[5].

The operational-functional component includes a set of techniques, methods and operations. With their help, a chess player achieves his goals and solves game problems during training and competitive activities.

The order of formation of logical methods of thinking was studied in detail by N.F. Talyzina (1984). She proposed the following hierarchy of logical operations: analysis and selection of the main thing, comparison, abstraction, generalization and concretization.

Summarizing the above, we can identify the main psychological and pedagogical conditions for constructing a system of educational and training tasks. These tasks are aimed at developing the strategic mastery of chess players. These conditions include:

1. Ensuring a high level of development of all components that make up the strategic mastery of chess players.
2. Consistent presentation of the material, taking into account the optimal pace of increasing complexity of tasks.
3. Identifying priority issues at each stage of a chess game. This takes into account their genesis and the gradual transformation of one stage into another.
4. Formation of generalized concepts that reflect the general direction of the strategy in the game.
5. Definition of theoretical relationships between different stages of the game and their specification.

6. Taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes (their chess style) when compiling an opening repertoire and choosing a strategy for conducting a game.

DISCUSSION

1. An analysis of psychological, pedagogical and specialized chess literature shows the following pattern. At the initial stages of long-term sports training of chess players with relatively low qualifications, the level of strategic mastery and sports results depend primarily on mastering the main (basic) techniques. At the same time, at the stage of sports improvement, additional techniques that determine the individual style of play of a particular athlete acquire decisive significance. These techniques can become a decisive factor in a chess match.

The level of strategic mastery of a chess player is determined by his compliance with the criteria laid down in specialized chess tests. It is also assessed by the final sports results. Strategic mastery is closely related to the level of intellectual, tactical and psychological preparation of the athlete.

2. The stage of sports improvement in the system of long-term training of chess players in children's and youth sports schools is characterized by a number of tasks:

- Attracting the optimal number of promising athletes to specialized sports training. This is aimed at achieving high and stable results, allowing them to join national teams.
- Achieving the "Master of Sports" standard with subsequent preparation for the title of "Grandmaster".

The solution to these problems is directly related to the formation of a high level of strategic mastery of chess players.

CONCLUSION

In Uzbekistan, the training of chess players is acquiring unique features due to national initiatives and programs aimed at popularizing and developing the art of chess. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 14, 2021 No. PP-4954, the country is implementing the State Program for the Development of Chess until 2025. This program includes the Chess in Schools project, which provides for teaching chess to students in grades 2–4 as part of the Physical Education subject in all secondary schools. For this purpose, 20 billion soums have been allocated from the state budget to provide schools with the necessary teaching aids and equipment. In addition, special attention is paid to the creation of children's and youth chess schools and clubs based on public-private partnerships. It is planned to open 25 such institutions, which will contribute to the formation of a solid infrastructure for the training of highly qualified chess players. An important aspect is the support of chess players with disabilities: a separate chess

division has been created within the structure of the National Paralympic Association of Uzbekistan. To increase interest in chess among various segments of the population, mass events are held annually, such as the “Mahalla Cup” among children and the “Chess Family” tournament among family teams. These initiatives help popularize chess and identify talented players at an early stage.

Thus, the uniqueness of the training of chess players in Uzbekistan lies in the comprehensive approach that combines educational reforms, infrastructure development and mass events aimed at the comprehensive development of the country's chess potential.

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